

Performance Evaluation of Equity-Linked Saving Schemes in India

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ABSTRACT

Mutual funds are the financial intermediaries that pool money from small investors and then they invest into different investment avenues. The mutual fund industry has seen an upward trend since 1963. The growth in the industry is seen due to the rise in private fund houses, increase in awareness by various fund houses and so on. Many investors have shifted their investments to mutual fund due to a higher growth potential of earning income and capital appreciation. ELSS is a tax saving Investment Avenue that is available to investors under section 80 C of income tax Act, 1961. The objective of this paper is to study the performance of ELSS on the basis of returns & risk adjusted measures and to know the degree of risk involved in ELSS. The Findings of this study will be useful to investors for their future investment decisions with respect to the selection of the ELSS schemes.

Key words: Mutual funds; ELSS & risk adjusted measures

1. INTRODUCTION

Mutual funds are financial intermediaries that pool the savings from the small investors and then invest them into different securities. A mutual fund is a type of investment in which investors pool their money together to buy a portfolio of stocks, bonds or other securities in order to take advantage of diversification and professional portfolio management at a reasonable cost. (What is a Mutual Fund?n.d.).

Mutual funds offer a wide variety of choice to investors such as Equity Funds, Equity Linked Savings Scheme (ELSS), Debt Funds, Liquid Funds, and Children Gift Funds and so on. Mutual Funds are easily accessible and one can start investing in mutual funds from anywhere in the world. An Asset Management Company (AMC) offers the funds and distributes through channels like Brokerage Firms, Registrars like Karvy and CAMS, AMC's, Online Mutual Fund Investment Portal, Agents and Banks (What Are The Advantages And Benefits Of Mutual Funds In India?, 2020). One can also transact mutual funds from NSE NMF platform and also from BSE platform, known as BSE Star. From NSE NMF, one can invest in mutual funds only after registering on the platform. Once, the investor is registered on the NSE NMF platform, one can perform a number of financial transactions such as new fund purchase, fresh purchase, additional purchase, redemption, switch transaction, systematic investment plan (SIP), systematic transfer plan (STP), systematic withdrawal plan (SWP) and non-financial transactions. Such platform also provide multiple payment options to an investor such as Cheque/ Demand Draft, RTGS / NEFT transfers, internet banking, Debit Card and ECS Mandate(NSE- Mutual Fund Platform, n.d.).

There are two ways of investing in mutual fund schemes – either by systematic investment plan (SIP) or via Lump Sum. SIP means investing a fixed sum of money regularly. On the other hand, in Lump Sum, the entire sum of money is invested at one time. An investor will make

good returns when he/she invests in mutual funds through SIP than via Lump-sum.

A SIP enables one to lower the average cost of investments and also reduces the risk of investment. This is possible through rupee-cost averaging. A SIP enables one to regularly increase the investment by a fixed amount and get the benefit of compounding as one earns returns on the returns generated by investments (Lump Sum or SIP – Which Will Give You Better Returns?, n.d.).

Many investors prefer to invest in mutual funds in order to save their income from taxes. Investors have to invest in Equity Linked Savings Scheme in order to claim deduction for a sum of Rs. 1, 50,000 from taxable income under section 80C of Income Tax Act, 1961. Such tax saving scheme has the potential to deliver good returns in the long run. Although risky, investment in ELSS has the potential to deliver significantly higher returns when compared to traditional tax saving instruments. Moreover, ELSS has the lowest lock-in period of three years which is lower than other tax saving avenues like NSC, PPF etc. (What is ELSS: Benefits, Taxation, Investment Guide & Returns, n.d.).

ELSS schemes are mostly invested in equity instruments. This will in turn provide a good chance of capital appreciation. An investor can get a lot of benefits through ELSS schemes like diversification is one of the biggest benefits that the investor can get as it invests in different companies of small-cap to large-cap and across various sectors. Most ELSS schemes allow investors to invest a small amount of Rs. 500 via SIP mode.

An investor should know some important concepts such as NAV, NFO, and AUM. NAV is the price of a single unit of the fund. When an Asset Management Company (AMC) launches a new scheme, it invites investment from people through an initial offer for subscription. This offer is known as a New Fund offer (NFO) (Basic Terms & Concepts of Mutual Funds, n.d.). A mutual fund pools money from investors and uses this money to buy assets like stocks, bonds and other securities.

The total value of the assets a fund buys is called the assets under management (AUM) (All you need to know before investing in Mutual Funds, n.d.). Mutual fund industry has witnessed a rising growth over the years due to increase in the private fund houses, rise in awareness spread by the fund houses, increase in SIP investments, and improvement in performance by the various schemes and so on. Many investors have shifted their investments from the saving bank account to liquid funds as it can fetch a higher return than a normal saving bank account. The wide variety of choices available to investors is another reason behind rise in investments in mutual fund industry. If one wants to buy some shares but has lack of knowledge of how the stock market works, then mutual funds is the best option as it is managed by professionals.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Lilly J. & Anusuya D. (2014) analysed the performance of selected ELSS Mutual fund schemes. They found that the LIC Nomura MF Tax plan growth and dividend schemes has outperformed well in the market when compared to other tax saving ELSS schemes. They have also found that only one scheme i.e. LIC Nomura MF Tax plan growth and dividend schemes has recorded the highest Sharpe, treynor & the sortino ratio. This shows that LIC Nomura Tax plan scheme can borne an adequate amount of risk when compared to other schemes.

Pathak R. (2018) analysed on the performance evaluation of ELSS Mutual fund schemes with special reference to Growth funds. It has found that ELSS –Growth funds have outperformed the benchmark index. Moreover there are funds like Axis long term equity

funds, IDFC Tax advantage and Franklin Templeton tax saver which had given good average returns and also excess return compared to government bonds. The researcher had also suggested that the investor should look into expense ratio before investing into any scheme, as it tell us about the fees charged by mutual fund houses.

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To evaluate the performance of Equity Linked Saving Schemes on the basis of returns.
- To find out the risk involved in various types of Equity Linked Saving Schemes by using Standard deviation & Beta.
- To evaluate the performance of Equity Linked Saving Schemes by using risk adjusted measures such as Sharpe ratio and Sortino ratio.

4. DATA & RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

- Data Collection-The data was collected from secondary sources such as journals and from the website of value research and money control.
- Analytical Tools-Different types of tools such as Standard Deviation, Hypothesis testing, Beta, Sharpe ratio, Sortino ratio are used in finding out the risk and performance of the funds.

5. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

- a) The study has been restricted to top 10 ELSS.
- b) The period is restricted to 5 years.

5.1.1. DATA ANALYSIS

5.1.1.1. Risk involved in various types of Equity Linked Saving Schemes by using Standard deviation & Beta.

Table I: Risk involved in various types of Equity Linked Saving Schemes by using Standard deviation & Beta.

Sr. No.	ELSS Schemes	(in percent)	
		Standard Deviation	Beta
1.	Bandhan ELSS Tax Saver Fund direct Plan (G)	13.37	0.9
2.	DSP ELSS Tax Saver Fund direct Plan (G)	15.18	1.01
3.	Kotak ELSS Tax Saver Fund direct Plan (G)	14.61	0.96
4.	Mirae Asset Tax Saver Fund direct Plan (G)	14.76	1
5.	SBI Long Term Equity Fund direct Plan (G)	15.1	1
6.	Motilal Oswal Long Term Equity Fund direct Plan (G)	19.53	1.08
7.	HDFC ELSS Tax Saver Fund direct Plan (G)	13.46	0.89
8.	Nippon India ELSS Tax Saver Fund direct Plan (G)	14.46	0.97
9.	Bank of India Tax Advantage Fund direct Plan (G)	17.05	1.07
10.	Quant ELSS Tax Saver Fund direct Plan (G)	16.93	1.08
	Category Average	14.74	0.96

Source: Money Control (n.d.) and Value Research (n.d.)

Table no. I clearly show the risk involved in various types of Equity Linked Saving Schemes by using Standard deviation & Beta. Motilal Oswal Long Term Equity Fund Plan (G) has recorded the highest standard deviation value that is 19.53 percent than the category average. It means that there is more risk involved in Motilal Oswal Long Term Equity Fund plan (G) than any other selected schemes. There is a risk of getting either more or less returns. Bandhan ELSS Tax Saver Fund Direct Plan (G) has the lowest standard deviation of 13.37 percent. This will in turn give stable returns to the investors.

With respect to beta (market risk), Motilal Oswal Long Term Equity Fund Direct Plan (G) and Quant ELSS Tax Saver Fund Direct Plan (G) have recorded the highest beta value of 1.08. It means that these funds carry higher market risk than the category average of 0.96. In contrast, HDFC ELSS Tax Saver Fund Direct Plan (G) has the lowest beta of 0.89, indicating lower market risk.

6.2. Returns generated in selected Equity Linked Saving Schemes

Table II: Returns generated in selected Equity Linked Saving Schemes

Sr. No.	ELSS Schemes	(in percent)		
		1 yr	3 yrs	5 yrs
1.	Bandhan ELSS Tax Saver Fund direct Plan (G)	5.54	16.37	16.43
2.	DSP ELSS Tax Saver Fund direct Plan (G)	3.21	20.7	17.61
3.	Kotak ELSS Tax Saver Fund direct Plan (G)	3.11	16.15	15.58
4.	Mirae Asset Tax Saver Fund direct Plan (G)	5.76	17.53	15.37
5.	SBI Long Term Equity Fund direct Plan (G)	3.96	22.13	19.2
6.	Motilal Oswal Long Term Equity direct Plan (G)	12.78	26.78	21.28
7.	HDFC ELSS Tax Saver Fund direct Plan (G)	-0.21	19.65	19.59
8.	Nippon India ELSS Tax Saver Fund direct Plan (G)	7.27	19.82	17.14
9.	Bank of India Tax Advantage Fund direct Plan (G)	9.74	19.73	17.22
10.	Quant ELSS Tax Saver Fund direct Plan (G)	10.62	19.92	19.76
	Category Average	3.79	17.07	15.52

Source: Money Control (n.d.) and Value Research (n.d.)

Figure 1: Annualized Percentage Returns for the last one year

Figure no. 1 shows the returns for the last 1 year ranges from -0.21 to 12.78 percent. Motilal Oswal Long Term Equity fund has given the highest return i.e 12.78 percent. This fund has outperformed benchmark index. On the other hand, HDFC ELSS Tax Saver Fund has given a very low return of -0.21%. Besides this, DSP ELSS Tax Saver Fund and Kotak ELSS Tax Saver Fund also remained below 4%, performing close to or below the category average.

Figure 2: Annualized Percentage Returns for the last three years

Figure no. 2 shows the compounded annualized percentage returns for the last three years ranges from 16.15 percent to 26.78 percent. The highest return of 26.78 percent is given by Motilal Oswal Long Term Equity Fund whereas Kotak ELSS Tax Saver Fund has given the lowest return of 16.15 percent. All the selected funds have outperformed the benchmark category average.

Figure 3: Percentage returns for the last five years

Figure no. 3 shows the compounded annualized percentage returns for the last five years ranges from 15.37 to 21.28 percent. Motilal Oswal Long Term Equity Fund has given the highest return of 21.28 percent for the last five years which is then followed by HDFC ELSS tax saver and Quant ELSS tax saver with 19.59 and 19.76 percent respectively. On the other hand, Mirae Asset Tax saver fund has given the lowest return of 15.37 percent for the last five years.

6.3. Performance of Equity Linked Saving Schemes by using risk adjusted measures

Table III: Performance of Equity Linked Saving Schemes by using risk adjusted measures

Sr. No.	ELSS FUND	Sharpe ratio	Sortino ratio
1.	Bandhan ELSS Tax Saver Fund direct Plan (G)	0.51	0.71
2.	DSP ELSS Tax Saver Fund direct Plan (G)	0.69	1.02
3.	Kotak ELSS Tax Saver Fund direct Plan (G)	0.46	0.62
4.	Mirae Asset Tax Saver Fund direct Plan (G)	0.54	0.76
5.	SBI Long Term Equity Fund direct Plan (G)	0.81	1.22
6.	Motilal Oswal Long Term Equity Fund direct Plan (G)	0.69	1.01
7.	HDFC ELSS Tax Saver Fund direct Plan (G)	0.77	1.13
8.	Nippon India ELSS Tax Saver Fund direct Plan (G)	0.64	0.96
9.	Bank of India Tax Advantage Fund direct Plan (G)	0.58	0.88
10.	Quant ELSS Tax Saver Fund direct Plan (G)	0.54	0.82
	Category Average	0.46	0.66

Source: Money Control(n.d.) and Value Research (n.d.)

SHARPE RATIO:-The Table no. III reveals that the sharpe ratio for 10 ELSS Schemes ranges from 0.73 to 1.27. SBI Long Term Equity Fund has recorded the highest Sharpe ratio i.e. 0.81 followed by HDFC ELSS Tax Saver Fund i.e. 0.77. On the other hand, Kotak ELSS Tax Saver Fund & Bandhan ELSS Tax Saver Fund has given the least Sharpe ratio. Higher

the Sharpe ratio higher is the performance of the schemes & higher risk adjusted performance.

SORTINO RATIO: - From the table, **SBI Long Term Equity Fund** is the best because it has the highest Sortino ratio (**1.22**). This means it gives good returns and avoids losses better than others. **Kotak ELSS Fund** has the lowest Sortino ratio (**0.62**), which means it is not as good in avoiding losses compared to others.

7. FINDINGS

7. 1.To evaluate the performance of Equity Linked Saving Schemes on the basis of returns.

- Most of the selected ELSS schemes have given good performance for the last 1 year, 3 years and 5 years as compared to the benchmark standard.
- Motilal Oswal Long Term Equity fund has given the highest return for the last 1 year, 3 years and 5 years.
- On the other hand, Axis long term equity fund has given the least return for the last one year, whereas ICICI prudential has given the least return for the last 3 and 5 years.

7.2. To find out the risk involved in various types of Equity Linked Saving Schemes by using Standard deviation & Beta.

- Motilal Oswal Long Term Equity Fund Plan (G) has recorded the highest standard deviation value that is 19.53 percent than the category average. It means that there is more risk involved in Motilal Oswal Long Term Equity Fund plan (G) than any other selected schemes.
- Bandhan ELSS Tax Saver Fund Direct Plan (G) has the lowest standard deviation of 13.37 percent. This will in turn give stable returns to the investors.
- With respect to beta (market risk), Motilal Oswal Long Term Equity Fund Direct Plan (G) and Quant ELSS Tax Saver Fund Direct Plan (G) have recorded the highest beta value of 1.08.

7.3. To evaluate the performance of Equity Linked Saving Schemes by using risk adjusted measures such as Sharpe ratio and Sortino ratio.

- a) Sharpe ratio- SBI Long Term Equity Fund has recorded the highest Sharpe ratio i.e. 0.81 followed by HDFC ELSS Tax Saver Fund i.e. 0.77. On the other hand, Kotak ELSS Tax Saver Fund & Bandhan ELSS Tax Saver Fund has given the least Sharpe ratio.
- b) **SORTINO RATIO:** - SBI Long Term Equity Fund has the highest Sortino ratio (1.22). Kotak ELSS Fund has the lowest Sortino ratio (0.62), which means it is not as good in avoiding losses compared to others.

8. CONCLUSION

The conclusion drawn from this study reveals that the most of the selected ELSS schemes have given good performance for the last 1 year, 3 years and 5 years. It is also found that some of the schemes have given the good results with respect to their risk adjusted measures like Sharpe ratio and SORTINO ratio. Motilal Oswal Long Term Equity Fund has given the highest standard deviation value i.e. 22.45% than any other selected ELSS schemes. The results showed the positive relationship between risk and return involved in ELSS schemes. ELSS schemes have a huge possibility to earn good returns in future as it is linked to the market. It is advisable to go for ELSS schemes than any other tax saving instruments since it is having the shortest lock-in period of 3 years.

9. RECOMMENDATIONS

- The mutual fund asset management companies should conduct awareness programs for the investors so that they are aware about the dual benefits of tax saving and capital appreciation in ELSS schemes
- The government should take more action to promote the ELSS schemes amongst the investors.
- Investors should invest in mutual fund schemes through online platforms since it is very convenient and time saving.
- Investors who are looking out for wealth plus tax saving should opt for ELSS schemes.

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